

Gastronomic Journeys: The Nexus of Experiential Marketing, Satisfaction, and Repurchase Intentions on GoFood and GrabFood

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the influence of experiential marketing through customer satisfaction on repurchase intentions for GoFood and GrabFood in the city of Mataram. This type of research falls under associative research. The population used in this study consisted of customers of GoFood and GrabFood in the city of Mataram, with a sample size of 100 respondents selected using purposive sampling technique. Data were collected through a questionnaire distributed via Google Form. The collected data were then analyzed using Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis, utilizing the AMOS software application. The results of the data processing indicate that the experiential marketing variable has a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions. However, customer satisfaction does not have a significant effect on repurchase intentions. This implies that the customer satisfaction variable does not mediate the influence of experiential marketing on repurchase intentions. This is due to the fact that customer satisfaction, as an intervening variable, does not significantly affect repurchase intentions.

1. Introduction

In this modern era, consumer behavior trends have undergone significant shifts, especially in the food and beverage industry sector. The advancements in technology and digitization have had a profound impact on how consumers order food and drinks. Online food ordering applications, such as GoFood and GrabFood, have become integral parts of urban lifestyles in many cities in Indonesia, including Mataram. The presence of these platforms provides consumers with the convenience of ordering food from various restaurants and eateries, along with a unique shopping experience.

In this context, the concept of experiential marketing has gained significant attention. Experiential marketing emphasizes creating deep and memorable positive experiences for consumers in their interactions with products or services. In the food industry, gastronomic experiences that engage the senses can significantly influence consumer perceptions of specific foods and brands. Therefore, it is important to understand the relationship between experiential marketing, consumer satisfaction, and the intention to repurchase on the GoFood and GrabFood platforms.

Marketing activities are now increasingly focusing on customer satisfaction. Understanding the factors that lead to customer satisfaction can lead to an intention to repurchase. This study focuses on the discussion that experiential marketing can be a strategy used by

marketers to enhance customer satisfaction and the intention to repurchase (Ellitan, 2022).

Efforts to enhance experiential marketing can increase customers' intention to repurchase if they feel satisfied with the products or services they consume (Ellitan, Sugiyanto & Risdwiyanto, 2022). Experiential marketing has an influence on repurchase intention, mediated by customer satisfaction (Fariisa, 2012). Customer satisfaction serves as a link between experiential marketing and repurchase intention (Oktafia, Ariningsih & Prasaja, 2023; Steven, Winoto & Purnama, 2022; Kartikasari & Nugroho, 2019). Customer satisfaction has been proven to have a positive and significant effect in mediating the relationship between experiential marketing and the intention to repurchase (Aditama & Haryono, 2022; Ardiyansah, 2021; Andrianto & Yuniarinto, 2017).

The research results of Mauladdawil & Nugroho (2023), Maharani, Rahadhini & Susanti (2020), and Febrini, Widowati & Anwar (2019) indicate that experiential marketing has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction, experiential marketing has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intentions, customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intentions, and customer satisfaction is able to mediate the marketing experience for repurchase intentions.

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In their study, Tuqa & Widyastuti (2022) demonstrated that Experiential Marketing has a significant influence on customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions, and customer satisfaction has a significant influence on repurchase intentions in the context of Grabfood services. There is a significant impact of Experiential Marketing on Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable (Tanu, 2019). The feeling derived from experiential marketing is an irreplaceable factor (Yang, 2009). Each construct of experiential marketing also exhibits a significant correlation between customer satisfaction and the intention to repurchase (Razi & Lajevardi, 2016).

Experiential marketing has an impact on consumers' intention to repurchase (Yanto, Lindawati & Pradana, 2020). Psychological factors such as senses, emotions, thoughts, and connection, collectively and gradually, influence consumer interest in making repeat purchases (Subawa, Widhiasthini & Suastika, 2020). Currently, discussions regarding consumer psychological factors persist and continue to evolve as they have been proven to influence consumer behavior (Oktriana, 2019).

However, Rahmania & Wahyono (2022); Marcellino, Ellitan & Muljani (2021) found contrary results, stating that experiential marketing does not have a significant influence on satisfaction. Similarly, Ardianto, Thalib & Riskarini (2021); Aziz (2015) in their studies stated that the experiential marketing variable does not have a significant influence on repurchase intentions. This could be due to a mismatch between consumer expectations and the actual experiences provided by experiential marketing strategies. If the experiences provided do not align with consumer expectations, this can reduce their level of satisfaction.

A re-evaluation of the impact of experiential marketing on satisfaction and repurchase intention is necessary due to significant disparities between the results and findings of previous research. Prior studies have provided initial insights into how experiential marketing can influence consumer perceptions of satisfaction and the intention to repurchase. However, new discoveries and potentially altered marketing contexts suggest that there might be potential outcome differences that need clarification.

In several earlier studies, it was found that experiential marketing had a positive impact on satisfaction and repurchase intention. However, in some other cases, research indicated that the influence of experiential marketing might not always be significant or even could have unclear effects on these variables. These differences could arise from variations in research methodologies, industry contexts, consumer characteristics, or marketing strategies employed.

Given the pivotal role of experiential marketing in supporting consumer satisfaction and loyalty, it is important to conduct more meticulous research while considering these factors. By identifying the factors that more deeply affect the impact of experiential marketing, this study will provide more accurate and valuable insights for marketing practitioners to optimize their strategies. Thus, revisiting the research on the influence of experiential marketing on satisfaction and repurchase intention is highly crucial to offer a more comprehensive understanding in this ever-evolving context.

The influence of experiential marketing on the level of satisfaction and repurchase intention through the GoFood and GrabFood platforms in Mataram holds significant implications for understanding consumer behavior dynamics in the current digital era. The concept of experiential marketing revolves around creating positive and memorable experiences for consumers through interactions with products or services. In the context of online food ordering, elements such as menu variety, appealing visual presentation, and smooth ordering experiences can contribute to a more satisfying gastronomic encounter for consumers. When consumers perceive positive and satisfying experiences while ordering food through GoFood and GrabFood, they

tend to develop a connection with the brand and the platform.

The positive experiences generated by experiential marketing can directly impact consumer satisfaction levels. Gastronomic experiences involving sensory and emotional aspects can establish an emotional connection between consumers and brands. When consumers feel content with their experiences, they tend to hold a positive perception of the quality of services and products offered by the platform. This consumer satisfaction, in turn, can influence their intention to repurchase. Consumers who are satisfied with their previous food ordering experiences through GoFood and GrabFood are more inclined to reuse the same platform in future transactions.

Hence, exploring the relationship between experiential marketing, consumer satisfaction levels, and repurchase intention on the GoFood and GrabFood platforms in Mataram will provide valuable insights for the development of more effective marketing strategies. Enhancements in gastronomic experiences, in terms of both product quality and interaction with the platform, can be key to building stronger consumer loyalty and driving business growth amid intensifying competition in the online food ordering industry.

The underlying issue that drives the importance of this research is how experiential marketing through GoFood and GrabFood platforms can influence consumer satisfaction levels within the context of gastronomic experiences, and how this level of satisfaction is related to consumers' intentions to repurchase. Given the tightening competition in the online food ordering industry, an in-depth understanding of these factors is crucial in devising effective marketing strategies and enhancing the competitiveness of these platforms in Mataram.

Despite online food ordering applications like GoFood and GrabFood becoming integral parts of urban life in Mataram, the lack of profound understanding of how the gastronomic aspects presented by both platforms empirically influence consumer perceptions and behaviors is a significant issue. Empirical data related to sensory and aesthetic aspects of the menus offered, visual food presentation, and the quality of the ordering experience provided by GoFood and GrabFood are still limited. Therefore, a question arises regarding the extent to which these factors genuinely impact consumer satisfaction levels and the intention to repurchase.

The scarcity of empirical data also inhibits the comprehension of consumer preferences regarding desired gastronomic experiences and how it correlates with the choice of a specific platform. This research aims to explore and understand how the gastronomic experiences generated by GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram contribute to consumer satisfaction and the intention to repurchase. This study will attempt to address these questions by delving into deeper empirical data regarding gastronomic factors on GoFood and GrabFood. It is hoped that this research will provide deeper insights into the role of experiential marketing in enhancing consumer interactions with online food ordering platforms and its impact on consumer loyalty in the current digital era.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Experiential Marketing

Experiential marketing is the process of identifying and satisfying consumer needs and beneficial aspirations, engaging consumers through two-way communication that brings brand personality characteristics and adds value to the target audience or customers (Smilansky, 2017; Sheu, Su & Chu, 2009; Heitzler, Asbury & Kusner, 2008).

Experiential marketing is an approach within marketing strategy aimed at recognizing and fulfilling beneficial consumer needs and expectations. This approach involves a two-way interaction with consumers, where the brand seeks to actively communicate with them. This is done with the purpose of conveying the unique personality traits

of the brand and also providing additional value to the target audience or customers.

Thus, experiential marketing focuses on creating positive and memorable experiences for consumers, which in turn can strengthen the relationship between the brand and consumers, as well as drive the intention to repurchase or further interact with the offered products or services.

2.2. Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction, as defined by Kotler & Keller (2012), is a customer's feeling where they can either feel pleased or disappointed with the outcomes obtained in comparison to the desired performance expectations.

Zeithaml (2000) explains that customer satisfaction is the result of comparing customer expectations with their perceptions of the actual performance of the product or service they receive. She describes that when actual performance exceeds expectations, customers will feel satisfied, whereas if actual performance falls below expectations, customers might feel dissatisfied. She also emphasizes the importance of understanding aspects that influence customer satisfaction, such as product or service quality, the price paid, and interactions with the company.

Understanding the contributing factors to customer satisfaction is crucial so that companies can better meet customer expectations and needs, which in turn will have a positive impact on customer retention and the long-term performance of the company (Homburg & Giering, 2001).

2.3. Repurchase Intention

Schiffman & Kanuk (2008) argue that repeat purchasing behavior occurs due to positive and satisfying experiences when customers use the provided products and services.

Chang & Chen (2008) in their research suggest that repurchase intention is a crucial indicator of customer loyalty towards a brand or product. They propose that repurchase intention reflects the consumer's evaluation of previous experiences with the product or brand, as well as the influence of factors such as satisfaction, product quality, and brand image. They also highlight the significant role of consumer trust in shaping repurchase intention. According to them, consumer trust in a brand or company can instill the belief that positive experiences will continue, thereby motivating the intention to repurchase.

Furthermore, Voss, Spangenberg & Grohmann (2003) state that repurchase intention is a behavioral response that emerges from the consumer's evaluation process of their experience and perception of a product or service. They argue that factors like satisfaction, product quality, and brand image play a pivotal role in shaping repurchase intention. They also emphasize the necessity of understanding the factors that influence repurchase intention so that companies can develop effective strategies to retain customers and enhance loyalty.

3. Research Method

In this study, the research design employed is associative or causal research. Sugiyono (2016) explains that associative research is a type of study aiming to understand the influence of one variable on another. This research can establish a theory to explain, predict, and control a phenomenon. The objective of this study is to determine the impact of implementing experiential marketing on customer satisfaction and its subsequent effect on repurchase intention in GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram.

Population refers to the entirety of all possible values, whether quantitatively or qualitatively measured, concerning specific characteristics of a complete object (Riduwan, 2008). The population is the generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that possess specific quantities and characteristics applied by researchers for study and subsequent conclusions (Sugiyono, 2016). The population in this research encompasses all consumers who engage in repurchase behavior on GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram.

Sample refers to a specific subset of the population that becomes the focus (Suharyadi & Purwanto, 2007). According to Arikunto (2010), a sample is a portion or representative of the population being studied. The determination of sample size is based on Bailey's opinion (2003), stating that the population is the total number of analysis units used. The designated sample size for this study is 100 respondents. This aligns with Bailey's (2003) notion that for research employing statistical data analysis, the minimum sample size is 30 respondents.

The data collection tool employed in this study is an online questionnaire. The questionnaire provided in this research comprises statements regarding the influence of Experiential Marketing, Satisfaction, and Repurchase Intention among the residents of Mataram. The questionnaire is distributed to respondents online through Google Form.

The statistical analysis technique utilized in this study involves the assistance of AMOS software. The initial step in SEM involves a theoretical identification of the research problem. The research topic is deeply examined, and the relationships among hypothesized variables must be supported by a robust theoretical justification. This is because SEM is used to confirm whether observed data align with theory or not. Thus, SEM cannot be employed to test imaginary causal hypotheses. This step is crucial and every relationship to be depicted in subsequent steps must be strongly supported by theory. In SEM analysis, there is no single statistical test to examine hypotheses regarding the model (Hair, et al., 1998), but various fit indices are employed to measure the degree of alignment between the presented model and the provided data (evaluating Goodness of Fit criteria).

The subsequent step involves interpreting the test results and model modification. Researchers can modify the model to enhance the composed model, with a vital note that any model changes must be supported by strong theoretical justification. No model modifications should occur without strong theoretical support. Model modification can be done by adding arrows between constructs (which can also represent the addition of hypotheses) or adding two arrows between indicators, which also must be supported by strong theory. The assessment of the feasibility of the modified model can be compared to the model before modification.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Data Analysis

The variables in this study consist of respondents' answers to the variables of experiential marketing, customer satisfaction, and repurchase intention regarding the products of GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram.

TABLE I. FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION SCORES

Variable	Score	Criteria
Experiential Marketing (X)	4.14	Good
Satisfaction (Z)	4.10	Good
Repurchase Intentions (Y)	4.14	Good

Source: data analysis results.

From Table I, it can be explained that the average score of responses for the experiential marketing variable is 4.14, which falls into the "good" category in relation to the implementation of experiential marketing for GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram. For indicator X1.1, the average score is 4.04, meaning that respondents consider their level of interest in the forms of GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram to be good. Indicator X1.2 has an average score of 4.22, indicating that respondents consider the taste of GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram to be very good. Indicator X1.3 has an average score of 4.05, meaning that respondents view the services of GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram to be good. Indicator X1.4 has an average score of 4.07, indicating that respondents consider the variety of GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram to be diverse and good. Indicator X1.5 has an average score of 4.31, meaning that respondents consider the product innovations presented to GoFood and GrabFood consumers in Mataram to be very good.

From the above table, it can be explained that the average score of responses for the customer satisfaction variable is 4.10, indicating that respondents are satisfied with GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram. For indicator Z1.1, the average score is 4.09, indicating that respondents are satisfied with the distinctive taste of GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram. Indicator Z1.2 has an average score of 4.21, indicating that respondents are very satisfied with the affordability of GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram compared to other products. For indicator Z1.3, the average score is 4.01, meaning that respondents are satisfied with the user interface convenience on the GoFood and GrabFood platforms in Mataram.

It can be explained that the average score of responses for the repurchase intention variable is 4.14, indicating that respondents express a high level of intention regarding repurchasing GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram. For indicator Y1.1, the average score is 4.05, meaning that respondents have a high intention of choosing GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram over other products. For indicator Y1.2, the average score is 4.15, indicating that respondents have a high intention of recommending GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram to others. Indicator Y1.3 has an average score of 4.19, meaning that respondents consider the search for detailed information about GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram (promotions, events, etc.) by consumers to be quite high. Indicator Y1.4 has an average score of 4.15, indicating that respondents have a high intention of repurchasing GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram.

Validity and reliability testing of the questionnaire were conducted to ensure that the instrument is accurate, reliable, and can be trusted as a tool for data collection. In this study, Pearson's product-moment correlation was used for validity testing, while the reliability test used the coefficient of reliability (Cronbach's alpha). Validity and reliability testing of the questionnaire were conducted using the SPSS for Windows program.

The validity testing results of the questionnaire for each indicator variable in this study are shown in the following table:

TABLE II. RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE VALIDITY TEST RESULTS

Item	r Value	r Critical	Criteria
X1.1	0.697	0.300	Valid
X1.2	0.782	0.300	Valid
X1.3	0.811	0.300	Valid
X1.4	0.659	0.300	Valid
X1.5	0.660	0.300	Valid
Z1.1	0.838	0.300	Valid
Z1.2	0.813	0.300	Valid
Z1.3	0.876	0.300	Valid
Y1.1	0.916	0.300	Valid

Item	r Value	r Critical	Criteria
Y1.2	0.908	0.300	Valid
Y1.3	0.958	0.300	Valid
Y1.4	0.958	0.300	Valid

Source: data analysis results.

From the validity testing results for the research questionnaire as shown in Table II, it can be determined that the validity testing results for the indicator variables of the research questionnaire as a whole are valid. This is indicated by the calculated r value being greater than the critical r value, or r calculated > 0.30 (Sugiyono, 2016).

The reliability testing results of the questionnaire for each variable in this study are shown in the following table:

TABLE III. RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE RELIABILITY TEST RESULTS

Variable	Alpha Cronbach	Alpha Critical	Criteria
Experiential Marketing (X)	0.782	0.600	Reliable
Satisfaction (Z)	0.843	0.600	Reliable
Repurchase Intentions (Y)	0.848	0.600	Reliable

Source: data analysis results.

Based on the table above, it shows that the alpha value is reliable, as it has an alpha above 0.60, making it suitable for the next stage. This is based on the opinion of Ghozali (2016), stating that the Cronbach's alpha value required to meet the reliability criteria is when the Cronbach's alpha value is above 0.60.

Model testing in SEM aims to assess the model fit. Based on the results of the model fit testing presented in Table IV, it is known that out of the eight criteria used to assess the suitability of a model, seven criteria are met, with only the AGFI criterion not meeting the requirement. Thus, it can be said that the model is acceptable, indicating a fit between the model and the data.

TABLE IV. SEM FIT INDEX

Criteria	Cut Of Coefficient Beta Value	Calculation Results	Description
Chi Square	Expected Small	62,989	Good
GFI	≥ 0,90	0,904	Good
RMSEA	≤ 0,08	0,059	Good
AGFI	≥ 0,90	0,841	Marginal
TLI	≥ 0,90	0,972	Good
NFI	≥ 0,90	0,927	Good
CFI	≥ 0,90	0,980	Good
CMIN/DF	≤ 2,00	1,340	Good

Source: data analysis results.

The SEM testing using the AMOS software yielded a structural equation model result illustrating the relationships between latent variables as shown in Figure 1:

FIGURE I. STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL

The next step involves conducting causality tests to examine the research hypotheses. From the appropriate model, each path coefficient can be interpreted. Based on Figure I, detailed interpretations of each path coefficient are presented in Table V:

TABLE V. RESULTS OF CAUSALITY TESTING FOR EACH PATH COEFFICIENT

Variable	Path Coefficient	CR	Probability	Description
X → Z	0,767	3,969	0,000	Significant
X → Y	0,645	3,215	0,001	Significant
Z → Y	0,229	1,636	0,102	Insignificant

Source: data analysis results.

The SEM analysis results indicate that experiential marketing has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction. This is evident from the positive path coefficient of 0.767 with a CR (Critical Ratio) of 3.969 (greater than 1.96), and a significant probability value (p) of 0.000 (value < α = 0.05). Thus, experiential marketing has a direct influence on customer satisfaction. This means that if consumers' perception of experiential marketing improves, their satisfaction with GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram will also increase. Conversely, if consumers' perception of experiential marketing decreases, their satisfaction will also decrease. This finding supports or confirms hypothesis 1 of the study, indicating a significant impact of experiential marketing on customer satisfaction for GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram.

Experiential marketing significantly influences repurchase intention, as evidenced by the positive path coefficient of 0.645 with a CR of 3.215 (greater than 1.96), and a significant probability value (p) of 0.001 (value < α = 0.05). Experiential marketing has a direct impact on

repurchase intention. This finding supports hypothesis 2 of the study, indicating that if consumers' perception of experiential marketing improves, their likelihood of repurchasing will also increase. Conversely, if consumers' perception of experiential marketing decreases, their repurchase intention will decrease. This occurs due to the effective implementation of experiential marketing by GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram, which provides tangible experiences before, during, and after product consumption, thus establishing a strong connection with consumers.

Customer satisfaction does not significantly influence repurchase intention in a positive direction. This is evident from the positive path coefficient of 0.229 with a CR of 1.636 (between -1.96 and 1.96), and a non-significant probability value (p) of 0.102 (value > α = 0.05). This result indicates that while an increase in customer satisfaction leads to a minor increase in repurchase intention (not significant), a decrease in customer satisfaction will also lead to a decrease in repurchase intention for GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram. This finding does not provide sufficient evidence to confirm or reject hypothesis 3 of the study.

The roles of experiential marketing and customer satisfaction in creating consumer repurchase can be inferred from the comparison between the direct influence of experiential marketing (exogenous variable) on repurchase (endogenous variable), and the indirect influence of experiential marketing on repurchase through customer satisfaction (intervening endogenous variable). If the direct influence of experiential marketing on repurchase is greater than the indirect influence, then the role of experiential marketing in creating repurchase is stronger. However, if the direct influence of experiential marketing on repurchase is smaller than the indirect influence, then the role of customer satisfaction in creating repurchase is stronger. This study's findings indicate that experiential marketing has the largest direct effect on repurchase, which contributes significantly to influencing repurchase intention for GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram.

Direct effects within the structural model of this study are observed between the exogenous latent variable of experiential marketing and the intervening endogenous latent variable of customer satisfaction, the exogenous latent variable of experiential marketing and the endogenous latent variable of repurchase intention, and the intervening endogenous latent variable of customer satisfaction and the endogenous latent variable of repurchase intention. Based on Table VI, it is determined that the direct effect of experiential marketing on customer satisfaction is 0.767 in a positive direction, the direct effect of experiential marketing on repurchase intention is 0.645 in a positive direction, and the direct effect of customer satisfaction on repurchase intention is 0.229 in a positive direction. The analysis results indicate that experiential marketing has the most significant direct effect on repurchase intention, making a substantial contribution to influencing repurchase intention for GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram.

TABLE VI. DIRECT EFFECT AMONG RESEARCH VARIABLES

Direct Effect	Exogen Variable	Endogen Variable	
		Satisfaction	Repurchase Intentions
Experiential Marketing		0,767	0,645
Satisfaction		0,000	0,229

Source: data analysis results.

Indirect influence occurs between the exogenous latent variable of experiential marketing and the endogenous latent variable of repeat purchase. Based on Table VII, it is revealed that the indirect influence of experiential marketing on repeat purchase is 0.176.

TABLE VII. INDIRECT EFFECT AMONG RESEARCH VARIABLES

Indirect Effect	Exogen Variable	Endogen Variable	
		Satisfaction	Repurchase Intentions
	Experiential		
	Marketing	0,000	0,176
	Satisfaction	0,000	0,000

Source: data analysis results.

Based on the comparison between the direct influence value and the indirect influence value of experiential marketing on repeat purchase (via customer satisfaction), it is evident that the indirect influence of experiential marketing on repeat purchase is smaller than its direct influence. Thus, it can be concluded that customer satisfaction does not play a higher role compared to the role of experiential marketing in generating repeat purchases on GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram City.

Furthermore, for the total influence between research variables, the analysis results are presented as shown in Table VIII below:

TABLE VIII. TOTAL EFFECT AMONG RESEARCH VARIABLES

Total Effect	Exogen Variable	Endogen Variable	
		Satisfaction	Repurchase Intentions
	Experiential		
	Marketing	0,000	0,821
	Satisfaction	0,000	0,000

Source: data analysis results.

The magnitude of the total influence is the sum of both the direct and indirect influences of all paths for each variable in this study. The calculation of the total influence, as shown in Table VIII, indicates that the influence of the experiential marketing variable on repeat purchase through customer satisfaction is known to have a positive path coefficient of 0.821. Therefore, it can be stated that there is a significant influence between experiential marketing and repeat purchase through customer satisfaction on GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram City.

4.2. Research Findings and Discussions

Based on the results of statistical analysis and hypothesis testing, it is known that there is a significant influence between experiential marketing and customer satisfaction. This is evidenced by the significance value being smaller than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). The findings of this study align with previous research conducted by Tuqa & Widayastuti (2022); Tanu (2019); Razi & Lajevardi (2016), where their research also found that the variable of experiential marketing significantly influences customer satisfaction.

The results of this study indicate that the experiential marketing strategies implemented by GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram City are capable of shaping customer experiences by creating distinctive and unique ideas. The experiences gained are likely to be remembered by customers. According to Smilansky (2017), customers today seek pleasant and lifestyle-aligned experiences rather than just the functional benefits of products.

This study supports prior research conducted by Mauladdawil & Nugroho (2023); Maharani, Rahadhini & Susanti (2020); and Febrini, Widowati & Anwar (2019), which concluded that experiential marketing is a crucial factor across all marketing aspects that impacts customer satisfaction and repeat purchases. In this study, experiential marketing is demonstrated to have a highly significant influence on customer

satisfaction. The increase in customer satisfaction can be attributed to the innovative concepts created by the management of GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram. The presence of positive and memorable experiences during the consumption of GoFood and GrabFood products contributes to heightened customer satisfaction.

Customer satisfaction is greatly influenced by a company's ability to provide emotional benefits that customers perceive when purchasing/experiencing their products. Emotional benefits can be created by delivering a positive and unforgettable experience that stands out from other vendors selling the same products. The stronger the experiential marketing provided by a company, the higher the likelihood that customers will experience satisfaction with each purchase. To build and maintain customer satisfaction, it's advisable for GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram to provide positive experiences and memories related to their products. This can be achieved by maximizing the five indicators of experiential marketing.

Based on the results of statistical analysis and hypothesis testing, it is evident that experiential marketing significantly influences repeat purchases. This is confirmed by the significance value being smaller than 0.05 ($0.001 < 0.05$). These findings align with research conducted by Yanto, Lindawati & Pradana (2020); Subawa, Widhiasthini & Suastika (2020); Oktriana (2019), which also found that the experiential marketing variable significantly influences repeat purchases. This is attributed to customers repeatedly consuming products of GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram when they experience the products' unique features.

According to Chang & Chen (2008), repeat purchasing is one of the consumer behavior attitudes where a consumer buys a product/service repeatedly without necessarily including a preference aspect. This leads to customer loyalty, which is a commitment to a specific brand or product, store, supplier, or company based on the positive attitude reflected in consistent repeat purchases.

The findings of this study also indicate that the implementation of experiential marketing strategies has a significant direct influence on repeat purchases. However, these strategies also have an indirect influence on repeat purchases, as customers experience satisfaction that aligns with their desires before making a repeat purchase, often even more. This is supported by the indirect effect results, indicating an indirect influence through customer satisfaction of 0.176, resulting in a total effect of 0.821.

The total effect value of repeat purchases is greater than the value of the direct influence of experiential marketing on repeat purchases. This aligns with the theory proposed by Schiffman & Kanuk (2008), stating that repeat purchases are a behavior that follows a previous purchase and is driven by satisfaction. If customers are satisfied, they are more likely to purchase again in the future.

Based on the results of statistical analysis and hypothesis testing, it is observed that the variable of customer satisfaction does not have a significant influence on repeat purchases. This is evidenced by the significance value being greater than 0.050 ($0.102 < 0.050$). These findings contrast with a study conducted by Ellitan, Sugiyanto & Risdiyanto (2022), which demonstrated a significant influence between customer satisfaction and repeat purchases.

Based on the research data, the path analysis results show a positive influence coefficient of 0.229 from customer satisfaction to repeat purchases. This result indicates that higher levels of customer satisfaction lead to increased customer loyalty, resulting in repeat purchases of GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram City. Achieving customer satisfaction is consistently followed by repeat purchases by customers.

This aligns with the theory presented by Zeithaml (2000), stating that one of the benefits of customer satisfaction is the potential for repeat purchases. Higher levels of customer satisfaction lead to increased customer loyalty, driving them to make repeat purchases from the same

source. Hence, it can be concluded that the higher the level of customer satisfaction with the company, the higher the rate of repeat purchases by customers of GoFood and GrabFood products in Mataram City.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of data analysis and the discussions presented earlier, the following conclusions can be drawn: 1) Experiential marketing has a significant influence on customer satisfaction; 2) Experiential marketing has a significant influence on repeat purchases; 3) Customer satisfaction does not have a significant influence on repeat purchases.

The test results demonstrate that experiential marketing strategies play a crucial role in enhancing customer satisfaction and repeat purchases. Therefore, it is advisable for GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram City to implement appropriate strategies to provide memorable product experiences and satisfaction to customers, encouraging them to feel content and make repeat purchases.

To enhance customer satisfaction, GoFood and GrabFood in Mataram City should focus on improving service quality. This can be achieved by enhancing customer facilities and providing services in accordance with established procedures. Factors affecting customer satisfaction can also be influenced by the responsiveness, understanding, and special attention given by customer service to customer concerns or complaints. These factors are vital for enhancing customer satisfaction and promoting repeat purchases.

In the conducted study, there are several limitations and weaknesses in the construction of this scientific article. The shortcomings and limitations of this study include its focus on only one independent variable, which is experiential marketing, and customer satisfaction as a mediating variable influencing repeat purchases. Future research should broaden the research scope to encompass a wider range of subjects and seek a more extensive population scope. Additionally, using a larger sample size can provide a more specific picture of the situation.

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